

The Advantages of Digital Literacy Strategies to Improve MSME's Business Performance

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Suggested Citation

Sitaniapessy, R.H., Latupapua, K.V., Lewaherilla, N., Leuherry, F., Ferdinandus, S.J., Asnawi, A. & Pentury, G. (2024). The Advantages of Digital Literacy Strategies to Improve MSME's Business Performance. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 504-512.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).43](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).43)

Abstract:

This study stems from the gap in research and expert opinions that explain the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance. This research was conducted in Maluku Province with research areas in West Seram Regency, Ambon City and Central Maluku Regency. To answer the research gap, we developed the concept of digital literacy strategic advantage rooted in Resource advantage Theory of Competition (Hunt&Morgan,1995). We used a sample size of 125 MSMEs spread across three city districts in Maluku province using a non-probability sampling technique with a non-proposive sampling approach. To test the

hypothesis, we used structural model analysis with the help of the AMOS SEM version 26 program. The results explained that the three hypotheses we proposed had a positive and significant effect on the business performance of MSMEs in Maluku province. Our theoretical implications and managerial implications are explained to be taken into consideration for theory development and MSME development.

Keywords: *Digital literacy strategy advantage, entrepreneurial orientation, digital knowledge sharing, MSME business performance.*

Introduction

Digital capabilities for a business organization in the current era are very important. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) that are able to develop digital capabilities will be able to achieve profit growth (P Foroudi, Gupta, Nazarian, & Duda, 2018) and create business sustainability (Denicolai, Zucchella, & Magnani, 2021). MSMEs or companies face quite high pressure with the presence of information technology that is developing very quickly which requires the company's ability to be able to develop its dynamic capabilities to face digital-based business transformation and utilize IOT and emerging technologies to share information

in real time (Fahrurrozi, Purwanto, Sitaniapessy, Roreng, & Toding, 2020).

Entrepreneurial orientation is an important factor in efforts to increase the success of a business, especially for businesses in the micro, small and medium economy. In this regard, small, micro and medium enterprises must be able to foster a good business mentality and ability that can increase business growth in a sustainable manner. Scientists in the field of marketing have widely researched the concept of entrepreneurial orientation to produce marketing performance levels for MSMEs; (Ferrerias-Méndez, Olmos-Peñuela, Salas-Vallina, & Alegre, 2021; Frank, Kessler, & Fink,

2010; Lekmat Laddawan, Selvarajah Christopher, & Hewege Chandana, 2018; Nasuredin, J., Halipah, A. H., and Shamsudin, 2016). These scholars have explained the results of their research with varying results in developing countries especially with regard to business performance.

The existence of MSMEs in business competition certainly requires every MSME to be able to overcome and protect its business from various possibilities that occur. Very intense competition can occur due to competition between the same industry, the emergence of new entrants in the business, the existence of substitute goods, the power of producers and the power of consumers. (Porter, 1985). These conditions make small and medium enterprises faced with very high competitive pressure. (Kraus, Rigtering, Hughes, & Hosman, 2012). Various studies have been conducted by various researchers with various perspectives to contribute to improving MSME business performance. Research related to the digital capabilities of MSMEs on business performance has been conducted in various perspectives with various consequences that arise. Research conducted by Benitez, Arenas, Castillo, & Esteves, (2022) explain that digitalization capabilities play an important role in the digital leadership relationship in achieving innovation performance. Human factors also play an important role in reflecting consumer orientation when delivering digitized services. ((Saunila, Ukko, & Rantala, 2019)).

Indonesia's digital index is still low despite the opportunity with a large population using the internet. According to a survey in 2022, Indonesia's digital literacy index score increased from 3.46 in 2020 to 3.54 in 2022 (statista.com) Based on the above issues, we conducted a study by trying to map digital capabilities that can encourage the performance of MSMEs. A lot of business development practices are severely constrained by the ability to manage businesses using digital platforms. This can be seen from the ability of MSMEs to transfer technology in marketing products, product financing and human resource development. The formulation of the research problem is how to improve

business performance with MSMEs built from entrepreneurial orientation The purpose of this study is to develop a new theoretical model to address the research gap between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance by developing the concept of digital literacy strategy excellence for MSMEs. To solve the above problems, especially the existence of varying results in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance, we use the Resource Advantage (R-A) of Competition Theory, developed by Hunt, & Morgan (1995). This theory describes a theoretical framework that views competitive advantage as the result of utilizing a firm's unique resources and capabilities. To test the development of the theoretical model, we developed the concept of strategic advantage of digital literacy, entrepreneurial orientation, digital knowledge sharing and business performance and implemented it on 125 MSMEs in Maluku Province, Indonesia.

Literature Review

The relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and digital literacy strategy excellence.

Entrepreneurial initiatives in organizations represent the basis of dynamic capabilities. (Mahringer & Renzl, 2018) explains First, environmental dynamism reduces the appropriateness of operating routines and capabilities. Second, entrepreneurial initiatives are triggered by operating routines and capabilities with respect to environmental dynamism. Third, entrepreneurial initiatives disrupt operating routines and capabilities and, thus, restore their fit in a dynamic environment. This paper contributes to current research on dynamic capabilities, micro-foundations and corporate entrepreneurship to create competitive advantage strategies. Research related to entrepreneurial orientation produces a strategic advantage for MSMEs as suggested by Sidik (2012) which explains market orientation as a business strategy is largely determined by entrepreneurial orientation, and the

characteristics of entrepreneurship itself; MSME competitive advantage requires the support of entrepreneurial orientation (Ong, Ismail, & Goh, 2010). So it can be concluded that:

H1: the better the entrepreneurial orientation, the better the digital literacy strategy excellence.

Relationship between digital knowledge sharing and digital literacy strategy excellence.

Digital knowledge sharing carried out by MSMEs where each person is an important factor in efforts to share various information into all parts of the organization. This knowledge sharing will result in technology transfer in the practice of entrepreneurial practices as part of digital knowledge Alford & Jones, (2020). Likewise, digital literacy as a digital culture that becomes an organizational culture in today's era which requires the ability of digital skills and knowledge on a regular basis is determined by the ability of various personal knowledge capabilities. The better the ability of various knowledge will produce a digital culture as part of the strategy advantage. (Swift & Hwang, 2008). Therefore, we can propose the following hypothesis:

H2: the higher the digital knowledge sharing, the better the digital literacy strategy.

The relationship between digital strategy literacy excellence and business performance.

With roots in the theory of R-A, which explains comprehensively that excellence in resources will result in financial performance. Digital technology, tangible assets and marketing capabilities play an important role as facilitators of firm growth (Pantea Foroudi, Gupta, Nazarian, & Duda, 2017). Digital transformation has a significant impact on a company's competitive advantage. Increased competitive advantage occurs through digitalization that supports companies in ensuring product quality and safety, and overcoming key challenges in various sectors (Chinakidzwa & Phiri, 2020). In addition, the use of digital technology to create innovative business models is strongly associated with business growth, suggesting that business innovation is one of the positive outcomes of digital transformation digital

(Berawi et al., 2020). Digital technology also has a positive influence on entrepreneurial orientation, and its use can be strengthened to improve entrepreneurial aspects in an organization (Berawi et al., 2020). (Berawi et al., 2020)

So the hypothesis we propose is:

H3. The better the excellence of digital literacy strategy, the higher the business performance.

Methods

Population, Sample, Sampling Techniques, Measurement Scale and Analysis Tools

Population is a collection of individuals or research objects that have predetermined qualities or characteristics. Based on these qualities and characteristics, the population can be understood as a group of individuals or objects of observation that have at least one characteristic in common (cooper dan Emory, 1981). The population was 1,308 small and medium enterprises in Maluku Province so that the sample size was set at 125. (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2014) state that the representative sample size for using SEM analysis is a minimum of 5 times the estimated parameters and a maximum of 10 times the estimated parameters. The sampling method is to use purposive sampling method. This method is a sampling method where the researcher has certain criteria or objectives for the sample to be studied). The criteria are as follows: (1) MSMEs that have a minimum workforce of 1 (one) person. (2) Has been operating for more than 1 year. This criterion is used to see how the development of SMEs for 1 year in running their business. The target sample in this study is the owner/manager of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) because they are the most responsible and knowledgeable about overall management both regarding human resources and capital issues. Questionnaires were distributed to all SMEs intentionally, and if they did not meet the requirements, other samples were taken as respondents. Variable measurement. The entrepreneurial orientation variable uses 3 question items which are used by

Sheu & Hu, (2009). The variable of various digital king knowledge uses 3 items used by (Bae, 2012; Hasyim & Yohanes, 2018). Variable quality is reached by Zhang, Wang, & Zhuang (2017). The business performance variable uses 3 question items that are used by Hasyim & Yohanes (2018). Variable advantages of digital literacy strategies used by (Feng, 2017; Pulendran, Speed, & II, 2003; Sweeney, Soutar, & McColl-Kennedy, 2011). The Business Performance variable uses question items developed by (Jayawarna, Jones, Lam, & Phua, 2014; Woodley, Burgess, Paguio, & Bingley, 2015) The measurement tool that will be used in this study uses interval data measurement... The interval scale is a data measurement that can produce data that has a range of values that have meaning, although the absolute value is less meaningful. This scale produces measurements that allow the calculation of averages, standard deviations, parameter statistics. Chorealization and so on. Data in the form of intervals can be generated with a technique, namely bipolar adjective. This scale is a refinement of the semantic scala data. The trick is to give only two extreme categories (Ferdinand, 2005).

Reliability, Validity and Variant Extract Tests

Reliability test is a measure of the internal consistency of the indicators of a construct that shows the degree to which each indicator indicates a common construct/factor. The limit used to assess an acceptable reliability stick is 0.70. Although this figure is not a "dead" measure. This means that if the research conducted is exploratory in nature, then a value below 0.70 is still acceptable throughout. The reliability test in Std Loading is obtained from the standardized loading for each indicator obtained from the results of computer calculations.

Research Results and Discussion

Respondent Profile

The profile of respondents who are sampled based on their position in the company, type of business, line of business, length of business.

The number of workers, marketing activities, technology used and the amount of profit earned each month. This figure shows that consumers who use digital technology have shown better results. This can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 1. Respondent Profile

Variables		%
Position	Owner	78.4
	Manager	12.7
	employee	8.8
Type of business	Family business	72.5
	Joint venture	27.5
Business fields	Food	53.9
	Fashion	19.6
	Others	26.5
Long Business	< 5 years	79.4
	6 – 8 year	12.7
	> 8 year	12.7
Labour	1 labour	42.2
	2 labour	28.4
	>= 3 labour	29.4
Marketing	Online	17.6
	Offline	9.8
	Onlne-offline	72.5
Technology	QRIS	14.7
	HP Android	58.8
	Transfer Bank	12.7
	Etc	13.7
Profit per month	< IDR 1.000.000	39.2
	IDR 1.000.001 – 3.000.000	41.2
	> IDR 3.000.000	19.6

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

After conducting confirmatory analysis and getting a fit model, each variable can be used to define latent constructs so that the full SEM model can be analyzed. Full SEM model results can be seen in Figure 1.

Evaluation of Data Normality

According to Hair et al (1998) SEM when estimated using maximum likelihood estimation, requires the fulfillment of the normality assumption. As explained in the previous chapter, the statistical value that can be used to test normality is the z-value. The commonly used rule of thumb is a critical value of ± 2.58 , meaning that we can reject the assumption of

normality at a probability level of 0.01 (Hair et al, 1998) Normality test of univariate and

multivariate data, the results are shown in table 2.

Figure1. Full Model of Digital Literacy Strategy Advantage

Table 2. Goodness of Fit Index Empirical Research

Goodness of fit index	Cut of value	Model result	Description
Absolute Fit Model			
X ² -Chi Square		59,525	The expected small value, X ² with a DF of 200 is 233.9 So it appears that the value of 207.348 is smaller than 233.9.
Degree freedom (DF)		50	
X ² -significance Probability	≥ 0,05	0,168	Fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 2,00	1,191	Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,039	Fit
GFI	≥0,90	0,932	Fit
Parsimonious Fit Measure			
AGFI	≥0,90	0,894	Fit (Marginal)
TLI	≥0,95	0,978	Fit
CFI	≥ 0,95	0,983	Fit

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the Chi-Square results of 207.348 with a probability of 0.346, which means that the hypothesized model is the same as the empirical data. Likewise, seen from other fit criteria: CMIN/DF, RMSEA GFI, CFI, TLI the results have met the predetermined requirements even though the AGFI value has not met the predetermined requirements.

Hypothesis testing in this model, it is necessary to test the null hypothesis which states that the regression coefficient between relationships is equal to zero through the t test which is common in regression model models (Ferdinand, 2005).

Table 3. Regression weight Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
DLA	<---	EO	,095	,199	,476	,634	Par_9
DLA	<---	DKS	,420	,243	1,729	,084	Par_11
BP	<---	DLA	,250	,082	3,069	,002	Par_10
EO1	<---	EO	1,000				
EO2	<---	EO	,852	,201	4,239	***	Par_1
EO3	<---	EO	1,328	,359	3,700	***	Par_2
DKS1	<---	DKS	1,000				
DKS2	<---	DKS	1,301	,242	5,371	***	Par_3
DKS3	<---	DKS	1,471	,263	5,581	***	Par_4
DLA1	<---	DKS	1,000				
DLA2	<---	DKS	1,191	,109	10,964	***	Par_5
DLA3	<---	DLA	,876	,093	9,446	***	Par_6
BP1	<---	BP	1,000				
BP2	<---	BP	,978	,086	11,350	***	Par_7
BP3	<---	BP	,657	,087	7,544	***	Par_8

Source: Primary Data Processed

The discussion of the results of hypothesis testing based on Table 3 is as follows:

The entrepreneurial orientation variable which consists of three indicators which include: (1) development of new ideas (2) able to see opportunities. (3) dare to take risks Digital literacy excellence variable (DLA) on 4 indicators consisting of: (1) adjustment with digital technology (2) adaptation to digital change (3) planning for the use of digital technology (4) ability to cooperate with suppliers digitally.

The results of statistical testing on this first hypothesis are the estimated parameter value of 0.095, standard error estimate of 0.199, critical ratio value of 0.476 with an error rate probability value of 0.634. By using an alpha of 0.05, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis which states that the higher the degree of entrepreneurial orientation, the higher the degree of digital literacy excellence can be accepted. This shows that the entrepreneurial orientation indicator can increase the superiority of digital literacy in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

The digital knowledge sharing variable is built from three indicators, namely (1) always sharing new knowledge. (2) exchanging information. (3)

solving problems together (4) learning to share ideas. While the digital literacy excellence variable (DLA) on 4 indicators consisting of: (1) adjustment with digital technology (2) adaptation to digital change (3) planning for the use of digital technology (4) ability to cooperate with suppliers digitally.

The statistical test results of this second hypothesis are the parameter value is 0.420, the standard error of the estimate is 0.243, the critical ratio value is 1.729 and the probability value of the error rate is 0.08. By using an alpha of 0.05, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis which states that the higher the digital knowledge sharing, the higher the digital strategy advantage can be accepted. This shows that the digital knowledge sharing indicator will increase the superiority of digital strategies in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Digital Strategy Excellence Variable 4 indicators consisting of: (1) adjustment with digital technology (2) adaptation to digital change (3) planning for the use of digital technology (4) the ability to cooperate with suppliers digitally. While business performance consists of (1) increased sales; (2) consumers are satisfied; (3) Consumers increase; (4) consumer loyalty.

The statistical test results of this third hypothesis are the parameter value is 0.280, the standard error of the estimate is 0.250, the critical ratio value is 3.069 and the probability value of the error rate is 0.002. By using an alpha of 0.05, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis which states that the higher the excellence of the digital strategy carried out by the company, the higher the company's business performance can be accepted. This shows that indicators of digital strategy excellence can improve business performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Conclusion

This study started from the research gap between the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance. Several studies have shown that there is inconsistency between entrepreneurial orientation and marketing performance. There are studies that explain that entrepreneurial orientation is able to produce marketing performance (Arshad, Rasli, Arshad, & Zain, 2014). While other studies explain that entrepreneurial orientation is not able to produce marketing performance, (Frank et al., 2017) (Lu & Zhang, 2016) and (Lekmat et al., 2018). From the various studies above, it can be concluded that the problem in this study is that there are still inconsistencies in views and research results between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance. Based on the data analysis process discussed in the previous chapter, the results of model testing and analysis are briefly presented in the following section. Model tested based on questionnaire data 125 respondents. The results of the full structural equation model analysis, the goodness of fit index is ChiSquare =59.525 degree of freedom = 50, probability =0.168; CMIN/DF=1.191; GFI=0.90; AGFI=0.894, TLI=0.970; CFI=0.983; RMSEA =0.039. This shows that the model is generally acceptable.

This research is based on the Resource Advantage Theory of Competition (Hunt, 2012). The resource-based view emphasizes the firm's resources as an important determinant of

competitive advantage and performance. There are two assumptions in analyzing the resources of competitive advantage as stated by Barney (1991) and Peteraf and Barney (2003). First, the model assumes that firms within an industry (or within a strategic group) may be heterogeneous with respect to the set of resources they control. Second, it is assumed that such resource heterogeneity may persist over time because the resources used to implement a firm's strategy are imperfectly mobile across firms (i.e., some resources are non-tradable and difficult to replicate). Source heterogeneity (or uniqueness) is considered a necessary condition for a set of resources to contribute to competitive advantage. The assumptions of heterogeneity and immobility are not, however, sufficient conditions for sustainable competitive advantage. According to Barney, (1991), a firm's resources must be valuable, rare, and not easily imitated and substituted in order to be a source of sustainable competitive advantage. Peteraf & Bergen (2003) present four conditions underlying sustainable competitive advantage: superior resources (heterogeneity within an industry), ex post limit to competition, imperfect resource mobility and ex ante limit to competition.

Acknowledgments

Thank you to the research and community service institutions and the master of management postgraduate study program for facilitating this research. Also to MSMEs who have been willing to become respondents and good cooperation in this research both online and offline.

References

- Alford, P., & Jones, R. (2020). The lone digital tourism entrepreneur: Knowledge acquisition and collaborative transfer. *Tourism Management*, 81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2020.104132>
- Arshad, A. S., Rasli, A., Arshad, A. A., & Zain,

- Z. M. (2014). The Impact of Entrepreneurial Orientation on Business Performance: A Study of Technology-based SMEs in Malaysia. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 130, 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.006>
- Bae, H. S. (2012). The effect of market orientation on relationship commitment and relationship effectiveness of port logistics firms. *Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, 28(1), 105–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajsl.2012.04.006>
- Benitez, J., Arenas, A., Castillo, A., & Esteves, J. (2022). Impact of digital leadership capability on innovation performance: The role of platform digitization capability. *Information & Management*, 59(2), 103590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.IM.2022.103590>
- Berawi, M. A., Suwartha, N., Asvial, M., Harwahu, R., Suryanegara, M., Setiawan, E. A., ... & Maknun, I. J. (2020). Digital Innovation: Creating Competitive Advantages. *International Journal of Technology*, 11(6), 1076–1080. <https://doi.org/10.14716/ijtech.v11i6.4581>
- Chinakidzwa, M., & Phiri, M. (2020). Impact of digital marketing capabilities on market performance of small to medium enterprise agro-processors in Harare, Zimbabwe. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(2), 746–757. <https://doi.org/10.3846/btp.2020.12149>
- Denicolai, S., Zucchella, A., & Magnani, G. (2021). Internationalization, digitalization, and sustainability: Are SMEs ready? A survey on synergies and substituting effects among growth paths. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 166, 120650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.TECHFORE.2021.120650>
- Fahrurrozi, M., Purwanto, M. R., Sitaniapessy, R. H., Roreng, P. P., & Toding, A. (2020). Study of marketing management using IoT. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(1), 294–297. <https://doi.org/10.31838/JCR.07.01.55>
- Feng, Y. G. Y. L. M. C. G. (2017). How does market learning affect radical innovation? The moderating roles of horizontal and vertical ties Purpose. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 32(1).
- Ferreras-Méndez, J. L., Olmos-Peñuela, J., Salas-Vallina, A., & Alegre, J. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation and new product development performance in SMEs: The mediating role of business model innovation. *Technovation*, 108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.TECHNOVATIO.N.2021.102325>
- Foroudi, P., Gupta, S., Nazarian, A., & Duda, M. (2017). Digital technology and marketing management capability: achieving growth in SMEs. *Qualitative Market Research*, 20(2), 230–246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QMR-01-2017-0014>
- Frank, H., Kessler, A., & Fink, M. (2010). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance — A Replication Study. *Schmalenbach Business Review*, 62(2), 175–198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03396804>
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Univariate Data Analysis. Exploratory Data Analysis in Business and Economics* (7th ed.). Pearson Education Limited 2014 All. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-01517-0_3
- Hasyim, & Yohanes, S. P. (2018). Marketing architectural capability and competitive networking in Indonesian fashion small and medium-sized enterprises. *Quality - Access to Success*, 19(166), 64–67.
- Hunt, S. D., & Morgan, R. M. (1995). Resource-Advantage Theory of Competition: Dynamics, Path Dependencies, Dimensions Evolutionary. *Journal of Marketing*, 60(4), 107–114.
- Jayawarna, D., Jones, O., Lam, W., & Phua, S. (2014). The performance of entrepreneurial ventures: Examining the role of marketing practices. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 21(4), 565–587. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-05-2014-0090>
- Kraus, S., Rigtering, J. P. C., Hughes, M., & Hosman, V. (2012). Entrepreneurial orientation and the business performance of SMEs: A quantitative study from the Netherlands. *Review of Managerial Science*, 6(2), 161–182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-011-0062-9>
- Lekmat Laddawan, Selvarajah Christopher, & Hewege Chandana. (2018). Relationship

- between Market Orientation, Entrepreneurial Orientation, and Firm Performance in Thai SMEs: The Mediating Role of Marketing Capabilities. *International Journal of Business and Economics*, 17(3), 213–237.
- Mahringer, C. A., & Renzl, B. (2018). Entrepreneurial initiatives as a microfoundation of dynamic capabilities. *Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change*, 14(1), 61–79. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-11-2016-0066>
- Nasuredin, J., Halipah, A. H., and Shamsudin, A. S. (2016). Entrepreneurial Competency and SMEs Performance in Malaysia: Dynamic Capabilities as Mediator. *International Journal of Research*, 3(4), 4759–4770.
- Ong, J. W., Ismail, H. Bin, & Goh, G. G. G. (2010). The Competitive Advantage of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) The Role of Entrepreneurship and Luck. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, vol 23, no, 373–391.
- Porter, M. E. (1985). Competitive Advantage. *Strategic Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb054287>
- Pulendran, S., Speed, R., & II, R. E. W. (2003). Marketing planning, market orientation and business performance, 37(3).
- Saunila, M., Ukko, J., & Rantala, T. (2019). Value co-creation through digital service capabilities: the role of human factors. *Information Technology and People*, 32(3), 627–645. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-10-2016-0224>
- Sheu, J. B., & Hu, T. L. (2009). Channel power, commitment and performance toward sustainable channel relationship. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 38(1), 17–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2007.07.003>
- Sidik, I. G. (2012). Conceptual Framework of Factors Affecting SME Development: Mediating Factors on the Relationship of Entrepreneur Traits and SME Performance. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 4, 373–383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(12\)00351-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(12)00351-6)
- Sweeney, J. C., Soutar, G. N., & McColl-Kennedy, J. R. (2011). The marketing practices-performance relationship in professional service firms. *Journal of Service Management*, 22(3), 292–316. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564231111136845>
- Swift, P. E., & Hwang, A. (2008). Learning, dynamic capabilities and operating routines. *The Learning Organization*, 15(1), 75–95. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09696470810842493>
- Woodley, C. J., Burgess, S., Paguio, R., & Bingley, S. (2015). Technology mentors: Enablers of ICT uptake in Australian small business. *Education and Training*, 57(6), 658–672. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-08-2014-0095>
- Zhang, T., Wang, X., & Zhuang, G. (2017). Building channel power: the role of IT resources and information management capability. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 32(8), 1217–1227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-12-2016-0286>